

LEarning and action alliances for NexuS Environments
in an uncertain future

LENSES

WP9

D9.6 LENSES Stories

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LENSES Stories (Podcasts, interviews & short videos)

Executive summary

The Mediterranean has been facing the depletion of natural resources from multiple pressures, which is why the LENSES project is making efforts to provide tools and solutions to restore ecosystems. This document presents some of the initiatives taken in our seven study areas in the Mediterranean region. We use innovative technologies and scientific approaches to overcome challenges related to the Water, Ecosystems, and Food (WEF) Nexus. We have found that a participatory approach is essential to success in ecosystem conservation efforts across the region.

LENSES Stories aim to raise awareness, support knowledge transfer through Learning and Action Alliances (LAA) and enhance the dissemination of results through case study success stories. These stories highlight the idea that all beings in society are interconnected and interdependent and serve as a communication tool to capture people's attention, engage their emotions, and convey complex ideas, leading to a shift in mindset towards Nexus thinking, and from there to Nexus acting (using tools and solutions provided by LENSES).

The building blocks of the LENSES Stories and success stories come from the seven pilot areas, which are Doñana (Spain), Menemen Plain (Türkiye), Hula Valley (Israel), Pinios (Greece): Delta and Agia, Koiliaris River Basin (Greece), Tarquinia Plain (Italy), and Deir Alla (Jordan). Several ambitious objectives have been set and will be achieved by applying System Dynamic Modelling (SDM), stakeholder participation, and Nature-based Solutions (NbS). The participatory approach of the Nexus is one of the keys to the project's success, as stakeholders are directly involved in the solutions.

D9.6 provides an overview of the seven pilot areas and potential success stories from each. It informs future actions and how to build confidence for good natural resource management in a feasible, integrated, and evidence-based way. This is the third version of the LENSES stories, and the process will continue until the end of the project. We trust learning as we go (learning by doing), and new videos and podcasts of efforts and lessons learned will follow until the project's completion.

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1. Introduction

The LENSES project is dedicated to creating effective strategies to enhance the resilience of Mediterranean regions during challenging times. The project employs different approaches and solutions to address these challenges and establish success stories based on its achievements.

As we know, the Mediterranean region is currently facing multiple pressures, such as the loss of ecosystems, conflicts over water resources and need to adopt practices that ensure the efficient use of natural resources. The impacts of climate change further compound these challenges, and there is an opportunity to manage resources better.

This is the **Final Version** of our **Deliverable 9.6 LENSES Stories**. It is the result of the collective effort of all the consortium, which began in month 15 (First version) and was refined by month 24 (Second version). This document highlights the improvements achieved, including a greater number of results and increased communication efforts to showcase the work of LENSES. The [project website](#), social networks ([Facebook](#), [LinkedIn](#), [Twitter](#)), and [YouTube channel](#) are being used to share results, videos, factsheets, and podcasts.

1.1. Purpose and Scope of D9.6

The aim of this document (**D9.6 LENSES Stories**) is to explore a range of success stories that illustrate how sustainable practices can contribute to overcoming different challenges and achieving project goals. The seven LENSES pilot projects represent unique examples of sustainability initiatives, including conservation, restoration, agroecological practices, and agrivoltaics, among others. By showcasing the success stories, we aim to promote sustainable practices and motivate people to replicate Nexus practices. The available material, such as videos, podcasts, factsheets, is key to raising awareness on Nexus issues. Figure 1 shows the overview of the LENSES stories and how they emerge from the work of the WPs. For a better understanding of the work packages, it is possible to watch a video of the stories of their activities, in addition in another video the project in general is commented.

- [LENSES Project Overview video.](#)
- [LENSES WPs Small Stories.](#)

Figure 1. Schematic overview of LENSES Success Story and relationships between work packages.

1.2. The concept of Pilot Stories

The issue of climate change requires more than just technical and innovative technologies. It is also a social problem that must be addressed with a participatory approach, and LENSES Stories can help to tackle these challenges.

Storytelling is a powerful tool to reach people and help to create holistic thinking. Pilot Stories illustrate the context of the Nexus thinking in the seven pilot areas and the current practice of thinking in separate silos in each domain of the WEF Nexus and raise awareness.

Science alone cannot achieve change. That is why achieving change depends on creating a narrative that resonates with society in general. We need stories that inspire people to create a sustainable future.

1.3. The structure of the document

The following chapters (2-8) provide a comprehensive overview of the materials that showcase the Pilot Stories within each designated pilot area. These materials include:

- A detailed factsheet (see [Annex](#)).
- Two videos dedicated to each pilot project, one of which features a succinct interview with the pilot leaders and the other a concise summary highlighting the main features and achievements of the pilot project and lessons learned.
- Podcasts are discussed in more detail in Chapter 10.

In addition, Chapter 8 serves to highlight the general similarities and differences between the pilot initiatives, providing a comparative analysis that enriches our understanding of their respective contexts and outcomes.

2. Doñana region in Spain

The Doñana pilot in LENSES includes the National Park, the Natural Park, areas of Natura 2000 Network (RN2000), and the basins which have intensive agriculture; Guadimar and Guadalquivir. Doñana is in southern Spain and is a UNESCO World Heritage Site due to its biodiversity and ecosystems. In recent years, it has unfortunately become a "hot topic" among politicians and has created a great debate around the water resources in the country's south. Its primary resources come from the Guadalquivir River and the aquifer, of which there is clear evidence of conflicts over water resources lately. Lately, illegal wells have been created that have had adverse effects on the area, threatening water availability. The need to balance economic development with environmental preservation in Doñana has become a contentious issue, which has attracted increased attention and controversy in recent times. There needs to be more agricultural planning and regulation in the region. In addition, there are pressures from mining, tourism, and climate change.

Figure 2. Doñana. Source: Estación Biológica de Doñana (<http://www.ebd.csic.es/inicio>), 2022.

There are a lot of pressures now, but it is worth pointing out the positive things and the effort that has been made. To preserve the ecosystems of Doñana, it must be said that work has been done on reforestation, wetland restoration and natural resource management by governmental entities, local communities, farmers and different environmental organizations. Hence, it is possible to highlight that the success stories in Doñana are the result of collaboration and joint efforts. Some promising initiatives are the *proper management of water resources, regulation of water extraction, the reduction of groundwater pumping and improvements in irrigation systems and large-scale nature restoration measures, including reconnecting the Guadimar river to the main wetland area inside the National Park*. Another clear example is *research*; The work being done in the project contributed to improving the understanding and knowledge of the importance of Doñana, making people continue to promote the care of the region and thus make better decisions.

Collaboration between stakeholders, which we are doing in the LENSES project, is essential to ensure long-term sustainability. Different institutions, communities and scientists have collaborated to ensure the proper management of the resources by carrying out awareness campaigns about the importance of Doñana. The essential point is that Doñana (National Park) is a UNESCO World Heritage Site, which provides an international legal framework that helps to raise awareness and facilitate these joint efforts.

2.1. Factsheet

Table 1. Relevant information on the Doñana factsheet.

Title: Addressing the sustainability of agriculture and ecosystem services in the Doñana Region		
Website Link: https://www.lenses-prima.eu/pilot-areas/guadalquivir-basin-spain/donana-region-pilot-related-documents/		

2.2. Video

Figure 3. First slide of the Doñana video.

Table 2. Relevant information on the Doñana video.

Title: Lenses Nexus stories: Doñana.
Respondent's name and organization: Manuel Bea – Eoadapta (https://www.lenses-prima.eu/partners/ecoadapta_team/).
YouTube Link: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=xRLT3ZpnFAU&t=1s
YouTube alternative video of Lessons Learned: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=PP3qkyEu_mA

3. Tarquinia Plain in Italy

The Tarquinia Plain is an essentially agricultural region of central Italy, with a favourable climate and fertile soils that make it an important agricultural area. Its ecosystems include unique habitats, coastal areas, wetlands, and protected areas such as the Tarquinia salt pans. The area faces several challenges, such as intensive agriculture, changes in land use, population growth, climate change, water stress due to overexploitation and high demand for water resources, all of which impact ecosystems. These problems require proper planning along with sustainable practices. The way to do this is through the active participation of local stakeholders and awareness of the importance of the main activities of the territory (agriculture, tourism) and its resources.

Figure 4. Field trip in the Tarquinia plain. Source: Pictures taken by the project partners, 2022.

Efforts in the Tarquinia Plain require vital priorities such as sustainable land use, protection of its ecosystems, conservation of its cultural heritage, promotion of good agricultural practices, a collaboration between different stakeholders and promotion of research and development (R&D). Nature-based solutions (NbS) are the backbone of our project and the core of Tarquinia's efforts. These solutions are the key components for LENSES Stories because they promote ecosystem protection and increase resilience in Tarquinia.

To give clear examples, the main stakeholders of the area (i.e., Municipality of Tarquinia, environmental association "Fare Verde" and Biodistretto "Maremma Etrusca e Monti della Tolfa", etc.) and CREA are making a great effort through analysis, conservation of the region, monitoring, studying how to promote sustainable practices, and clearly understanding the ecosystems of the region to inform proper planning and management. We thank the people dedicated to conserving this unique area who have shown us their landscapes.

3.1. Factsheet

Table 3. Relevant information on the Tarquinia factsheet.

Title: Addressing the sustainability of agriculture and ecosystem services in the Plain of Tarquinia		
Website Link: https://www.lenses-prima.eu/pilot-areas/tarquinia-plain-italy/tarquinia-plain-pilot-related-documents/		

3.2. Video

Figure 5. First slide of the Tarquinia video.

Table 4. Relevant information on the Tarquinia video.

Title: Lenses Lexus stories: Tarquinia
Respondent's name and organization: Stefano Fabiani – CREA (https://www.lenses-prima.eu/partners/crea_team/).
YouTube Link: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=BDqTfm-zBnQ
YouTube alternative video of Lessons Learned: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=gv2UwBTmzvK

4. Menemen Plain in Türkiye

The Menemen Plain, located in the western part of the country, is crucial for the agricultural sector in Türkiye. This pilot faces several environmental problems and challenges, such as population growth, loss of agricultural land, habitat fragmentation, alteration of natural ecosystems, intensification of agriculture, overuse of agrochemicals, water scarcity, poor resource management and, of course, climate change. However, some conservation efforts to promote sustainability and resilience are underway in the Menemen Plain, including measures such as proper planning, sustainable agricultural practices, water resource management, biodiversity conservation and climate change adaptation. These efforts involve the active participation of local communities, government agencies, research institutions and other stakeholders to address challenges and promote sustainability.

Figure 6. Menemen Plain. Source: UTAEM, 2022.

Success stories in Menemen involve implementing sustainable land use practices, water resource management and biodiversity conservation through stakeholder collaboration. Success stories include the *promotion of sustainable agricultural practices* (e.g., organic farming, agroforestry and integrated pest management), *effective water management practices* (water-saving irrigation techniques, groundwater control and regulation, and watershed management), *protection and restoration of natural habitats* (e.g., wetlands, marshes and forests), *climate change adaptation measures*, *local capacity building and stakeholder collaboration*. The last one, participatory approaches (LAA), is a central aspect of the LENSES project because we believe that we can raise awareness and promote sustainable practices through this approach.

4.1. Factsheet

Table 5. Relevant information on the Menemen factsheet.

Title: Enhanced Water-Ecosystem-Food-Climate Nexus system for Gediz Basin.	
Website Link: https://www.lenses-prima.eu/pilot-areas/gediz-basin-turkey/gediz-pilot-related-documents/	

4.2. Video

Figure 7. First slide of the Menemen video.

Table 6. Relevant information on the Menemen video.

Title: Lenses Nexus stories: Gediz.
Respondent's name and organization: Zübeyde Albayram Doğan – UTAEM (https://www.lenses-prima.eu/partners/utaem_team/).
YouTube Link: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=N34WXqnt14&t=3s
YouTube alternative video of Lessons Learned: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=aXHgtgZBYiw

5. Pinios River Basin in Greece: Delta and Agia

The Pinios River is the longest in Thessaly, a region in central Greece, and its Delta and Agia region are critical ecosystems with rich biodiversity and cultural assets. Both are the "sub-pilots" of LENSES and constitute two highly productive sub-basins, which face several sectoral problems, including occasional water shortages in Delta, deteriorating water quality, environmental degradation, declining agricultural production and reduced net income over time. Research and identification of the sectoral problems faced, as well as the interdependencies and cross-sectoral conflicts perceived by stakeholders, along with the development of Nature-based Solutions to mitigate the vulnerabilities of pilot areas, aim to successfully build coherent and resilient agricultural societies and preserve natural ecosystems under the climate crisis.

SWRI is leading these efforts and involves collaboration between stakeholders to address issues and promote sustainable practices in both regions through outreach activities, including field trip, young farmers seminars, foreign students' education trips and café meetings, thematic discussions, the LENSES Pinios window and workshops.

Figure 8. First technical workshop in Pinios. Source: Pictures taken by the project partners, 2022.

A potential success story in conserving the Pinios Delta and Agia region in Greece is the implementation of conservation measures, which have yielded positive results in improving the area's ecological health. Some of the current conservation efforts in the Pinios Delta and Agia region include improvement of water management practices (one of the main solutions within the LENSES project), measures to reduce pollution from agricultural runoff, agricultural management practices, reduction of agricultural inputs and footprint, improvement of soil properties, optimization of production costs, development of adaptation plans, stakeholder engagement, and awareness and education campaigns being conducted to increase public awareness of the ecological importance of the Pinios Delta and Agia region.

These measures are intended to address the range of challenges facing both sub-pilots and promote sustainable management practices indeed.

5.1. Factsheet

Table 7. Relevant information on the Pinios factsheet.

Title: Tackle the Water-Ecosystem-Food (WEF) Nexus challenges in the pilot area of Pinios hydrologic observatory.

Website Link: <https://www.lenses-prima.eu/pilot-areas/pinios-catchment-area-greece/pinios-pilot-related-documents/>

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Project pilot Areas: Pinios Hydrologic Observatory (Greece)

5.2. Video

Figure 9. First slide of the Pinios video.

Table 8. Relevant information on the Pinios video.

Title: Lenses Nexus stories: Pinios.

Respondent's name and organization: Vassilios Pisinaras- SWRI (https://www.lenses-prima.eu/partners/swri_team/).

YouTube Link:
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=G2OYK8-R3VA>

YouTube alternative video of Lessons Learned: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=_gTNTS3uXGE

6. Hula Valley in Israel

This pilot, unlike the others, is on a small scale and is in the Hula Valley in Israel. Although it is an experimental area, its results are intended to cross borders in the Mediterranean and perhaps beyond. The Hula Valley is home to a variety of flora and fauna, including many species of migratory birds. As historical context, the Hula Valley was once a large lake that was drained in the 1950s for agricultural purposes but has been partially restored. The agricultural sector is significant in the region with established and technified irrigation systems. Several challenges can be highlighted, such as climate change, habitat loss, ecosystem problems due to water diversion and drainage, and declining water quality.

We want to find renewable energy sources throughout the world and in the Mediterranean area and create a tangible link with agriculture. In this pilot, we evaluate the possibility of diversifying agriculture with energy production and making farms self-sufficient. Benefits we are looking for include mitigating climate change by reducing the carbon footprint, reducing dependence on fossil fuels, and improving adaptation to climate change, and also socio-economic benefits by diversifying and ensuring farmers income.

Figure 10. Field visit to the Agrivoltaics experimental area and the Hula Valley in Israel. Source: Pictures taken by the project partners, 2023.

The **Energy-Agriculture-Water-Climate Nexus** is represented in this pilot within a strong link between energy and agriculture; Agrivoltaics are undoubtedly a success story in the Hula Valley, as it supply the needs of farmers, ensuring food as well as energy security, with less impact on the environment. Agrivoltaics provides multiple benefits, and this pilot is expected to have success stories: shade impact assessment on crops, creation of microhabitats, less water consumption (as evapotranspiration is less), protection of crops from extreme weather events, and carbon sequestration. Agrivoltaics in the Hula Valley are a success by providing a sustainable approach to energy generation while contributing to local economic benefits and producers.

6.1. Factsheet

Table 9. Relevant information on the Hula factsheet.

Title: Innovative solutions assessment in the Hula Valley: Agrivoltaics	
Website Link: https://www.lenses-prima.eu/pilot-areas/hula-valley-israel/hula-valley-pilot-related-documents/	

6.2. Video

Figure 11. First slide of the Hula video.

Table 10. Relevant information on the Hula video.

Title: Lenses Nexus stories: Migal.
Respondent's name and organization: Uri Marchaim – MIGAL (https://www.lenses-prima.eu/partners/migal_team/).
YouTube Link: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=gtFOYNACS1k&t=1s

7. Koiliaris River Basin in Greece

The Koiliaris River Basin is located on the island of Crete, Greece. The river originates in the White Mountains, which reach altitudes of over 2000 meters. Currently, the basin is affected by multiple problems, and overexploitation of groundwater is one of them. Also, desertification and runoff from extreme events due to climate change exceeding infiltration rates represent unprecedented challenges.

The Technical University of Crete (TUC) and LENSES partners aim to protect the region by promoting sustainable practices, conserving ecosystems, and supporting local stakeholders. The focus is on applying innovative methodologies and strategies, such as Nature-based Solutions (NbS) that have now gained enormous popularity, water management practices, sustainable land use planning, and environmental awareness of farmers. Nexus' analysis in this pilot project is particularly interested in avocado cultivation, evaluating different ways to help farmers increase profitability and get them to adopt better management practices.

Figure 12. Koiliaris River Basin. Source: Technical University of Crete, 2022. Source: TUC, 2022.

Koiliaris has a concise history of rich and unique ecosystems, resources, and high cultural assets; economic activities include agricultural production and tourism. Here, solutions involve a combination of strategies to enhance the region's resources. Therefore, strategies either enhanced all of its futures or are no longer applicable.

Success stories in the Koiliaris River basin involve a combination of measures, such as NbS, water management practices, sustainable land use planning, raise awareness, and stakeholder engagement. The Technical University of Crete is leading these efforts working collaboratively with farmers' associations and various stakeholders to mitigate the adverse effects of climate change and other challenges.

7.1. Factsheet

Table 11. Relevant information on the Koiliaris factsheet.

Title: Optimizing the Water-Ecosystem-Food-Climate Nexus in Avocado Plantations.	
Website Link: https://www.lenses-prima.eu/pilot-areas/koiliaris-crete/koiliaris_pilot_related_documents/	

7.2. Video

Figure 13. First slide of the Koiliaris video.

Table 12. Relevant information on the Koiliaris video.

Title: Lenses Nexus stories: Koiliaris
Respondent's name and organization: Nikolaos Nikolaidis – TUC (https://www.lenses-prima.eu/partners/tuc_team/).
YouTube Link: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=x11cTa6RleI&t=19s
YouTube alternative video of Lessons Learned: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=URCbJKYsY3c

8. Deir Alla in Jordan

The pilot of Deir Alla is in the Jordan Valley and is known for its cultural relevance and for being an area in which agriculture stands out as one of the main economic activities. A large percentage of the population lives from agriculture and animal breeding. Although water is scarce in the Jordan Valley, this area is characterized by being an intensive irrigated land. Water resources are under various pressures due to over-abstraction, pollution, and competition between water users (e.g., industrial, domestic and agriculture). Unsustainable agricultural practices, such as the excessive use of fertilizers and pesticides, contaminate water sources, affecting the local environment.

In this region, there are not only problems with water resources, but also energy security issues, and it is affected by population growth and climate change. To further assist farmers, the NARC team is currently working on formulating a more economical and sustainable feed ration for livestock. Farmers are making better use of water to produce silage as an intercrop and reduce the production costs of the livestock system, which are often very high.

Figure 14. Field day coordinated by the NARC team. Source: Pictures taken by the project partners, 2023.

Success stories in Deir Alla come from supporting farmers to become more sustainable in their practices and farmers are expected to cooperate in different ways and for different purposes. Success depends on multi-stakeholder collaboration and effective management approaches. NARC is a clear example of successful initiatives that can be achieved by working closely with farmers under the demands and constraints of the challenges. Success stories include exploring and promoting new crops and applying crop rotation practices, as they can be a significant achievement. The integration of leguminous crops, such as alfalfa and vetch, can increase the availability of high-quality forage for livestock. This can reduce dependence on costly external sources of livestock feed and improve the overall economics of livestock production. Promoting alternative crops well adapted to local Agro-ecological conditions can diversify farmers' income sources and reduce the

risk associated with monoculture production. Through extensive research, NARC conducts field experiments and engages farmers to identify suitable crops and ensure their sustainability.

8.1. Factsheet

Table 13. Relevant information on the Deir Alla factsheet.

Title: Intercropped, Crop Rotation for Silage Making Using Mixed Water Quality: Development Of Feed Quality Software.	
Website Link: https://www.lenses-prima.eu/pilot-areas/middle-jordan-valley-jordan/middle-jordan-valley-pilot-related-documents/	

8.2. Video

Figure 15. First slide of the Deir Alla video.

Table 14. Relevant information on the Deir Alla video.

Title: Lenses Nexus stories: Deir Alla.
Respondent's name and organization: Sami Awabdeh – NARC (https://www.lenses-prima.eu/partners/narc_team/).
YouTube Link: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Db7JQTemYuc
YouTube alternative video of Lessons Learned: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=XSdwyFA4uF8

9. Similarities and Differences Across Pilots

This section highlights some similarities and differences that can be observed when analysing in further detail. Understanding the main characteristics can help to identify opportunities in each zone and thus achieve replicable success stories.

Pilots included in the figure are Doñana in Spain, Pinios and Koiliaris in Greece, Tarquinia in Italy, Deir Alla in Jordan, Hula in Israel, and the Menemen Plain in Türkiye.

Figure 16 represents seven study areas that have unique biodiversity-rich systems and ecosystems. At the same time, their natural resources are under pressure from human activities and climate change. These pressures imply the creation of joint efforts to address the challenges through innovation, science, sustainability, and the implementation of plans to use natural resources efficiently.

There are also differences between the study areas; however, they are all located in the Mediterranean region; these are six different countries with diverse economic, social, and political approaches (even different continents) where the priorities of each zone depend on their unique challenges, resulting in different approaches such as wetland restoration, agriculture, production, and the search for renewable energy sources, among others. Ecosystems are also diverse, and the level of stakeholder involvement varies from one area to another.

Figure 16. Similarities and Differences across LENSES pilots.

10. Podcasts: LENSES Stories

This section presents the "LENSES Stories" podcasts, in which we explore the intricate Nexus approach in the Mediterranean. This series of podcasts illustrates the interconnectedness between water, ecosystems, and food, highlighting the transformative power of NbS, from collaboration and innovation to policy frameworks and financing. It is possible to access through our YouTube channel, Lenses Prima.

10.1. Episode 1

Podcast Title: The Nexus Approach in the Mediterranean: An Introduction

Release Date: Already Uploaded. February 12th, 2024.

Description: In the first episode of "LENSES Stories," the Nexus approach's importance in the Mediterranean has been introduced. Exploring the interconnectedness of water, ecosystems, and food, emphasizing the role of NbS in addressing regional challenges. Highlighting the need for collaboration and innovation.

Link to Episode: [YouTube channel: Lenses Prima.](#)

Duration: 2:33

Figure 17. Episode 1 The Nexus Approach in the Mediterranean.

10.2. Episode 2

Podcast Title: Nature-Based Solutions: Transforming the Nexus in the Mediterranean

Release Date: Upload by March 5th, 2024.

Description: The second episode of "LENSES Stories" explored NbS and their impact in the region. Highlighting examples such as wetland restoration and renewable energy projects, we emphasize the role of NbS in addressing complex challenges such as water scarcity and climate change. The importance of collaboration through LAA and the use of PSDM for informed decision making is also highlighted.

Link to Episode: [YouTube channel: Lenses Prima.](#)

Duration: approx. 3 minutes.

Figure 18 Episode 2 Nature-based Solutions.

10.3. Episode 3

Podcast Title: Learning and Action Alliances: Collaborating for Nexus Success

Release Date: Upload by March 12th, 2024.

Description: The third episode of “LENSES Stories” focused on collaboration and participation throughout the project. LAAs are a central aspect of LENSES, where stakeholders find spaces to discuss open and freely about challenges and can also be part of the solutions, within the PSDM, their perspectives built the model and based on the results decision makers can have a clear understanding on policy impacts. This episode emphasizes the need for active participation in all aspects of the project within the WEF Nexus sectors.

Link to Episode: [YouTube channel: Lenses Prima.](#)

Duration: approx. 3 minutes.

Figure 19. Episode 3 Learning and Action Alliances.

10.4. Episode 4

Podcast Title: Participatory Dynamic Systems Modelling: Understanding Nexus Interactions

Release Date: Upload by March 19th, 2024.

Description: The fourth episode highlights the importance of stakeholder participation in building and simulating models using the PSDM approach. This approach requires understanding the various variables involved in each Nexus sector and how they interact. The episode also discusses how PSDMs offer a holistic assessment of the potential impacts of nature-based solutions across multiple sectors and allow us to identify synergies and trade-offs, ensuring that integrating solutions aligns with the broader goals of WEF management.

Link to Episode: [YouTube channel: Lenses Prima.](#)

Duration: approx. 3 minutes.

Figure 20. Episode 4 Participatory Dynamic Systems Modelling.

10.5. Episode 5

Podcast Title: Inspiring Success Stories: Nature-Based Solutions in the Mediterranean

Release Date: Upload by March 26th, 2024.

Description: Episode five focuses on NbS, and strategies implemented in the Mediterranean region. The episode highlights efforts from seven pilot areas, such as wetland restoration in Doñana Park (Spain) and water management strategies in the Hula Valley (Israel). The episode emphasizes that these strategies aim to promote sustainability, biodiversity, and agricultural resilience, ultimately benefiting society.

Link to Episode: [YouTube channel: Lenses Prima.](#)

Duration: approx. 3 minutes.

Figure 21. Episode 5 Inspiring Success Stories.

10.6. Episode 6

Podcast Title: Policy and Governance Frameworks: Scaling Up Nature-Based Solutions

Release Date: Upload by April 2nd, 2024.

Description: Episode six of "LENSES Stories" focused on policy and governance frameworks for scaling up NbS in the Mediterranean. It explored how robust policies, collaborative governance, and inclusive decision-making can foster widespread adoption and create a more resilient region.

Link to Episode: [YouTube channel: Lenses Prima.](#)

Duration: approx. 3 minutes.

Figure 22. Episode 6 Policy and Governance Frameworks.

10.7. Episode 7

Podcast Title: Financing Nature-Based Solutions: Investing in a Sustainable Future

Release Date: Upload by April 9th, 2024.

Description: In the seventh episode, we talked about the significance of financing and investment in promoting the adoption of NbS. It explored innovative financing mechanisms and strategies to acknowledge the value of nature in addressing nexus challenges. The topics covered include the link between financing and NbS, unlocking resources through innovation, and highlighting the multiple benefits of these solutions through collaboration.

Link to Episode: [YouTube channel: Lenses Prima.](#)

Duration: approx. 3 minutes.

Guests:

- Linda Barci (ETIFOR) Environmental Economics Analyst, MSc in Resource Economics and Sustainable Development.
- Juan Diego Restrepo (ETIFOR) Forest Engineer, Specialist in Project Management and MSc in Sustainable Tropical Forestry.

Figure 23. Episode 7 Financing Nature-based Solutions.

10.8. Episode 8

Podcast Title: Nature’s Benefits: Exploring Ecosystem Services in the Mediterranean.

Release Date: Upload by April 16th, 2024.

Description: Episode 8 explores the role of Ecosystem Services and their importance in sustaining life. Ecosystem services provided by nature, such as clean water, climate regulation, pollination, and soil fertility among others. It highlights how these services contribute to human well-being, biodiversity conservation and economic prosperity. Through real-life examples and an expert opinion from the University of Padova, the episode highlights the need to recognize, protect and sustainably manage ecosystem services for a region that can meet present and future challenges.

Link to Episode: [YouTube channel: Lenses Prima.](#)

Duration: approx. 3 minutes.

Guest: Giorgia Bottaro (UNIPD) Postdoctoral researcher at the University of Padova, Ecosystem Services Expert.

*PODCASTS
LENSES STORIES*

Esteban Henao Giorgia Bottaro

EPISODE 8. Nature's Benefits: Exploring Ecosystem Services in the Mediterranean

 This project is part of the PRIMA programme supported by the European Union.

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Figure 24. Episode 8 Nature's Benefits.

11. Conclusions

The LENSES project aimed to produce a set of Pilot Stories to showcase the benefits and impacts of utilizing tools and methodologies to manage natural resources. These stories aimed to simplify complex examples and case studies, highlighting the advantages of using appropriate resource management practices. The third and final version of the "LENSES Stories" (D9.6) contributes to developing success stories that promote collaboration between local stakeholders to achieve sustainable resource management. The LENSES project analysed success stories in seven study areas representative of the Mediterranean region, including Doñana in Spain, Tarquinia in Italy, Menemen in Türkiye, Pinios in Greece (Delta and Agia), Hula Valley in Israel, Koiliaris in Greece, and Deir Alla in Jordan. The research identified several requirements for success stories, including sustainable practices and actions taken to address challenges and achieve positive impacts. These actions range from ecosystem protection to stakeholder engagement and policy interventions, highlighting the various approaches to protecting the region's resources. Although progress has been made toward sustainability, challenges such as climate change, habitat degradation, unsustainable practices, population growth, economic development pressures, and geopolitical dynamics remain. Addressing these challenges and building on successes ensures the continuity of success stories. The success stories demonstrate the potential for achieving sustainability and conservation goals through collaboration and innovative strategies, such as LAA, NbS, and PSDM. Based on the findings of D9.6, it is recommended that initiatives focused on participatory approaches involving stakeholders be continued. Fostering international collaborations, sharing best practices, and knowledge transfer between LENSES pilots can further enhance success stories. LENSES success stories serve as a valuable tool for demonstrating the benefits of sustainable resource management and can be a powerful way to communicate scientific knowledge to society. By highlighting sustainable practices and actions taken to address challenges, these stories can raise awareness of the importance of sustainable management among stakeholders.

12. Bibliography

LENSES Grant Agreement. LENSES Consortium Agreement between the CREA and the LENSES partners.

Korten, D. C. (2015). *Change the Story, Change the Future: A living Economy for Living Earth*. Berrett-Koehler Publishers.

13. Annex

13.1. Doñana Factsheet

the
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Project pilot Areas: Doñana (Spain)

ADDRESSING THE SUSTAINABILITY OF AGRICULTURE AND ECOSYSTEM SERVICES IN THE DOÑANA REGION

The pilot area includes the Doñana marshlands, one of the most valuable wetlands in the Mediterranean region, being the wintering site for more than 500,000 waterfowl each year. Moreover, the region is the largest berry producer and one of the essential rice cultivation areas across Europe. Climate change and intensive use of resources are seriously compromising the sustainability of irrigated agriculture and the conservation of the environmental heritage of Doñana. Novel and holistic solutions and approaches are required to ensure the resilience of the whole agro-ecological system.

GENERAL CHARACTERIZATION

- ✓ The pilot area encompasses the Doñana National and Natural Parks as well as the cultivation areas sharing water resources (i.e., surface and groundwater) with the Doñana natural space.
- ✓ **Location:** South-West of the Iberian peninsula, within the Andalusia region.
- ✓ **Main economic activities:** Agriculture and (eco)tourism.
- ✓ **Area:** 3,700 km².
- ✓ Doñana is a UNESCO World Heritage site because of its exceptional value for in situ conservation of biological diversity.
- ✓ More than 8,500 ha of berries, 23,000 ha of rice and 15,000 ha of woody crops are irrigated in the Pilot area.
- ✓ The official Drought Emergency Plan is currently activated.

LENSES GOALS

Contribute to improving water resources management by creating a systemic view to help address Nexus challenges:

- ✓ Sustainable high-value agricultural activity in a context of water scarcity exacerbated by climate change.
- ✓ Better adaptation to more frequent and intense droughts.
- ✓ Guaranteeing ecological services (i.e., provision, regulation, cultural) from Doñana natural space, currently limited by a decrease in rainfall and water contribution.
- ✓ Improved water allocation between competing activities.
- ✓ Identification of consensus desired futures.

HOW WILL LENSES WORK?

Considering all the targets, the priority actions being implemented in Doñana focus on identifying strategies to overcome existing challenges. Our approach is based on the elaboration of PARTICIPATORY SCENARIOS and PATHWAYS towards increased system resilience and enhanced sustainability of the Water-Ecosystems-Food systems.

Through participatory scenarios, we understand the result of adding: (1) Consensus visions (i.e., desired futures) and descriptive narratives for these visions. (2) A validated explanatory model (i.e., a Participatory System Dynamic Model) provides a basis for quantitative analysis and simulates and visualises scenarios that help steer the stakeholder discussion for consensus visions.

By pathways, we understand a well-defined set of suitable policy actions that can potentially lead to desired scenarios (visions). This participatory approach is supported and builds upon LENSES solutions: climate risk assessment, water accounting and water balance simulations, and the identification of suitable Nbs bundles.

FUTURE PERSPECTIVE "CALL TO ACTION"

"Doñana is a singular area facing complex and impending challenges, exacerbated by climate change. LENSES adopts a strongly participatory approach and a holistic perspective for improving the understanding of interactions (trade-offs and potential shared benefits) among water allocation, ecosystem services, food production and climate adaptation. The setting of this common ground will allow building suitable scenarios strengthening the system resilience and clear pathways to reach these scenarios."

Ecoadapta Team

ECOADAPTA is a non-profit organization with the objective of promoting the advancement of knowledge-transfer on climate change adaptation and the action towards sustainability and increased resilience of socio-ecological systems.

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13.2. Tarquinia Factsheet

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Project pilot Areas: Tarquinia Plain (Italy)

ADDRESSING THE SUSTAINABILITY OF AGRICULTURE AND ECOSYSTEM SERVICES IN THE PLAIN OF TARQUINIA

Being one of the most extensive agricultural production area of the Lazio Region (Italy), the plain of Tarquinia is currently facing the deterioration of the quality of its water resources, while farmers are dealing with increasing energy costs for pumping water from local irrigation networks. This scenario is further worsened by extreme weather events, such as flooding and drought, which are becoming increasingly frequent in the area, thus compromising tourism and agriculture, the two main economic sectors of the territory.

GENERAL CHARACTERIZATION

- ✓ Tarquinia is part of **UNESCO World Heritage**.
- ✓ **Location:** Central Italy, Lazio Region, around 90 km north of Rome.
- ✓ **Main economic activities:** Tourism and agriculture.
- ✓ **Area:** 27.000 ha, 85% of which are designated as nitrate vulnerable zone. 67% of the territory is agricultural area, of which almost 10.000 ha irrigable, and 3.000 ha irrigated mainly with micro-irrigation systems.

LONG OLIVE TRADITION

LENSES GOALS

Contribute to improve water resources management and be part of the solution addressing Nexus challenges □

- ✓ Structural and management issues + High pumping energy costs = Difficult to meet water summer demand.
- ✓ Contamination of groundwater by nitrates. Soil degradation problems due to intensive agriculture.
- ✓ Agricultural enterprises' contraction associated with reduction in the Utilised Agricultural Area (UAA).
- ✓ Complex technological modernization due to scattered distribution around the territory.
- ✓ Agricultural producers are often excluded due to their size compared to the large operators in the sector.

HOW WILL LENSES WORK?

Considering all the targets, the priority actions implemented in Tarquinia must focus on:

- ✓ Involve a multi-stakeholders working group to identify main challenges and barriers for a sustainable employment of natural resources in the area, which prevent the further development of the two key economic sectors (agriculture and tourism) and discuss possible strategies to overcome them.
- ✓ Raising awareness of stakeholders and end-users on innovative and easily implementable technical solutions and sustainable management practices useful for protecting, restoring or enhancing the status of natural resources in the area, with a focus on water management.
- ✓ Boost the adoption or scaling up of sustainable and integrated management practices (e.g. early warning systems for extreme weather events), aiming at increasing use efficiency of natural resources and especially of water, based on NEXUS approach, in the context of climate change.

FUTURE PERSPECTIVE "CALL TO ACTION"

"The project aims to identify innovative and easily implementable technical solutions and sustainable management practices, and to boost their adoption or scaling up within the area, with the final aim to protecting, restoring or enhancing the status of natural resources at local level. The objective will be achieved through an integrated and participatory approach, which brings together a large variety of stakeholders, going beyond mere development and sharing of best practices, rather producing shared knowledge and encourage action towards common goals".

CREA Team

COUNTRY PILOTS REGIONAL TEAM

CREA conducts studies and researches on local agricultural and forestry ecosystems, with the aim to characterize them and to build space-time models through an inter- and multidisciplinary approach, ultimately supporting their sustainable management.

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13.3. Menemen Factsheet

the LENSES project

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Project pilot Areas: Menemen Plain in Gediz Basin (Turkey)

ENHANCED WATER-ECOSYSTEM-FOOD-CLIMATE NEXUS SYSTEM FOR GEDIZ BASIN

There is a periodic water shortage due to drought, affecting producers and frequent in recent years due to climate change. The use of irrigation methods is unconscious and excessive, so producers in the outflow parts of the irrigation network cannot access sufficient water. High groundwater levels are observed in the lower parts of the basin due to winter rainfall hindering production and causing drainage problems in the crop plots. In addition, soil salinity caused by excessive summer irrigation is another challenge. The pilot focuses on adopting basin-wide agricultural management systems to ensure sustainable agriculture and food supply and contribute to socio-economic development within the framework of environmental awareness and cooperation.

GENERAL CHARACTERIZATION

Menemen Plain In Gediz Basin →

- ✓ Area of Menemen: 694.49 km².
- ✓ Population: 193,229.
- ✓ Main income: Agriculture and polyculture (carried out on an area of 16.500 ha).
- ✓ Main crops: Cotton, wheat and maize also types of vegetables and fruits.
- ✓ Mediterranean climate is dominant.
- ✓ The Gediz River is the main source of water for irrigation in Menemen Plain. Irrigation is mainly furrow-irrigation, and less than 10% comes from groundwater.
- ✓ Home to the "Bird Paradise", which is a RAMSAR site since 1998, accommodating various bird species, some of which are in endangered or threatened status.

LENSES GOALS

- ✓ Contributing to Nexus analysis using data from tools such as Ecosystem-based hydrological models, surveys, terrestrial observations, remote sensing and GIS.
- ✓ Improving Nexus management for the assessment of ecosystem services coupled with a Hydrological model in order to determine priority areas in pilot area.
- ✓ More effective use of irrigation water to cope with drought management and feasible planning of water allocation with cooperation. Groundwater resource levels and usable water quality will be determined and their effective use will be ensured.

HOW WILL LENSES WORK?

Planning of **Nature-based Solutions (Nbs)** to address the challenges experienced ☐

- ✓ Limit or prevent specific uses and practices.
- ✓ Maintain and enhance natural wetlands.
- ✓ Natural protected area network structure.
- ✓ Agro-ecological practices.
- ✓ Change crop rotations.
- ✓ Soil improvement and conservation measures.
- ✓ Agro-ecological network structure.
- ✓ Increase soil water holding capacity and infiltration rates.
- ✓ Incorporating organic matter
- ✓ Use soil conservation measures - Deep-rooted plants and minimum or conservation tillage.
- ✓ Integrated coastal zone management.

Work to improve Nexus dialogues ☐ It is aimed to create Active Learning Action Alliances with the participation of stakeholders and decision makers from all relevant sectors.

FUTURE PERSPECTIVE "CALL TO ACTION"

It is necessary to identify needs and develop suggestions to solve existing problems of all components within the Nexus. The harmonization of knowledge sharing, and data allows a further step towards solving the problem areas. Stakeholders need to embrace sustainable production by applying good practices; questioning commonly known truths and using innovative techniques is vital. Learning and action partnerships should occur where the ideal method with a nature-based solution can be determined for stakeholder and decision-maker engagement. Dissemination of good practices that strengthen the Nexus in the Gediz basin will be ensured."

UTAEM Team

PILOT TEAMS

The International Agricultural Research and Training Centre (UTAEM), Menemen-İzmir, operates within the General Directorate of Agricultural Research and Policies of the Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry with experience in conducting several international projects as a partner in sustainable soil and water management, water resources systems, climate change and remote sensing.

Ea-Tek is a spin-off company with roots and still active links to the Water Resources division of the civil engineering department of Dokuz Eylul University in Izmir-Turkey. The team members have expertise in water resources management, sustainability and multi-criteria decision making in water resources systems, remote sensing and image processing, water balance and quality modelling, environmental data management and GIS applications.

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13.4. Pinios Factsheet

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Project pilot Areas: Pinios Hydrologic Observatory (Greece)

TACKLE THE WATER-ECOSYSTEM-FOOD (WEF) NEXUS CHALLENGES IN THE PILOT AREA OF PINIOS HYDROLOGIC OBSERVATORY

In recent years, a significant effort has been put into improving the understanding of the Water-Ecosystem-Food (WEF) Nexus system as a framework to promote sustainable development. Agia watershed and Pinios Delta located in Thessaly region, Greece, constitute highly productive sub-basins, encountering several sectoral problems, including occasional water shortage and quality deterioration, environmental degradation, and agricultural production decrease and net income reduction over time. Investigation and identification of the sectoral problems faced, and the cross-sectoral interdependencies and conflicts sensed by stakeholders, along with the development of Nature-based Solutions to mitigate the vulnerabilities of the pilot areas, aim at successfully building coherent and resilient agricultural societies, and preserving natural ecosystems under climate crisis.

GENERAL CHARACTERIZATION

PINIOS DELTA

- ✓ **Highly productive plain** of about 75 km²
- ✓ **Annual crops** are dominating, mainly. Sunflower and corn. Kiwi fruit is also upscaling.
- ✓ **Irrigation from groundwater and surface water – lack of infrastructure**
- ✓ **Water salinisation issues.**

AGIA WATERSHED

- ✓ **Area:** Approx. 53 km²
- ✓ **International Long Term Ecological Research (ILTER) Site**, highly instrumented area.
- ✓ **Agriculture is dominant.** Orchards mainly, apples and cherries.
- ✓ **Irrigation from groundwater.**

LENSES GOALS

The LENSES project will contribute to all the Nexus domains' challenges. In particular:

 Water □ Provisioning to protection and improvement of the water bodies' statue, Sustaining a sufficient quantity and quality of water to meet the needs of water users; Developing management practices to address salinity problems in the delta plain; Introduce agro-ecological and irrigation practices to reduce water consumption from the agricultural sector, Improve water resources management adaptability to climate change.

 Ecosystem □ Maintain environmental flow; Improve management of produced agricultural residues; Improve the NATURA 2000 protected area preservation.

 Food □ Maintain agricultural production; Improve the viability and competitiveness of the agricultural sector; Optimize production costs; Promote the quality elements of local products to increase their added value in the market.

PRIMA
PROGRAMME FOR RURAL INNOVATION AND RURAL DEVELOPMENT
IN THE MEDITERRANEAN AREA

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 PRIMA
PROGRAMME FOR RURAL INNOVATION AND RURAL DEVELOPMENT
IN THE MEDITERRANEAN AREA

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HOW WILL LENSES WORK?

- ✓ **Plan Nature-based Solutions based (NBS) measures to address the identified vulnerabilities and challenges in the pilot areas**
 - Considered NBSs include: ✓ Agroecological approaches focusing on irrigation practices improvement; ✓ Increase of soil water holding capacity and infiltration rates; ✓ Incorporation of manure, compost, biosolids or crop residues to enhance carbon storage; ✓ Mulching; ✓ Use of soil conservation measures – Cover crops; ✓ Soil improvement and conservation measures mainly through conservation tillage.

- ✓ **Drive Nexus Dialogue**
 - A broad range of stakeholders from all sectors, levels and functions are engaged supporting the Active Learning & Action Alliance development, aiming at collective learning of stakeholders.

FUTURE PERSPECTIVE “CALL TO ACTION”

“Each area, each farmer, and every citizen calls for special attention and individualized design of solutions tailored to the specific needs of the people who live and experience the day-to-day problems to be tackled and adapted to the capacity of the ecosystem. Science, can and does provide valuable data, advanced methodological approaches, experience and expertise in best practices, hi-end solutions and advanced technological tools that are needed in environmental problem solving and management. Still, the secret ingredient is not kept by the scientists, but the society itself. Active stakeholders’ engagement is the road to fully comprehend the needs and the dense web of inter-sectoral relations that characterizes each particular study area. Based upon them, we may safely design viable, practicable and realistic solutions that are suitable to the needs and born by nature: Natural Based Solutions. This is their ecosystem, their space and their call to where they wish to steer. They know by tradition the values and virtues of their land, the capacity and self-healing power of nature. We are providing the navigation tools and together we built a brighter and more sustainable future that will ensure the safety of the NEXUS sectors”.

SWRI Team

COUNTRY PILOTS REGIONAL TEAM

The Soil and Water Resources Institute (SWRI) is one of the 11 research institutes of the Hellenic Agricultural Organization-DEMETER in Greece that specializes on the protection and management of soil and water resources. SWRI is involved in resource management and policy support oriented projects, focusing on environmental modeling, applying state-of-the-art technological solutions and sensors in environmental monitoring, developing and proposing good agricultural practices, performing climate change impact assessment and environmental impact assessment in agriculture, and managing soil resources in agricultural areas. SWRI is one of the founding partners and the operator of the Pinios Hydrological Observatory (PHO), which is included in the International Long-Term Ecological Research (ILTER) sites and the European Network of Hydrological Observatories (ENOHA). SWRI also manages national river discharge monitoring network operating in the framework of the WFD 2000/60/EU .

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13.5. Hula Valley Factsheet

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Project pilot Areas: Upper Galilee, Hula Valley (Israel)

INNOVATIVE SOLUTIONS ASSESSMENT IN THE HULA VALLEY: AGRIVOLTAICS

Desalinated water as an alternative has increased the price of water for farmers, and climate change-induced water scarcity has evolved in the Upper Galilee in recent decades, apart from pressures on food security, resulting in changing cropping patterns; therefore, innovative strategies that integrate water, energy and food security are needed. The goal should be to offer novel solutions, with innovative thinking, for the sustainable use of agricultural land. One such solution is Agrivoltaics. This technology will improve energy availability in the Water-Ecosystem-Food-Climate Nexus and enable the sustainable development of the rural ecosystem by adding a source of income.

GENERAL CHARACTERIZATION

The Hula Valley →

- ✓ **Location:** Northern part of the Dead Sea Valley.
- ✓ **Area:** 177 km².
- ✓ **Mountains of the valley:** The Golan Heights and the Naftali Mountains of the Upper Galilee.
- ✓ The valley occupies most of the course of the **Jordan River** (length of 25 km).
- ✓ **Agriculture:** **Winter crops** ☐ Wheat, oats, alfalfa, clover, onions, garlic / **Summer crops** ☐ Sunflower, peanuts, cotton, chickpeas, watermelon / **Crops for the food industry** ☐ Potatoes, carrots, peas, tomatoes, corn, beans / **Perennial crops** ☐ Avocado, apples, pears, stone fruits and citrus.

LENSES GOALS

One of the main objectives of LENSES is to improve the understanding of the Nexus, which is Solutions that integrate the different domains are key. The need for more efficient production, minimizing water use and environmental impact will be addressed.

Main objectives ☐

- ✓ Improve the use of water resources.
- ✓ Reduce carbon footprint, GHG emissions and local electricity consumption.
- ✓ Integration of new methodologies.
- ✓ Reducing the use of fertilizers, pesticides and herbicides.
- ✓ Implementation of Earth Observation (EO) and drones to monitor crop productivity.
- ✓ The pilot consider various temporal and spatial scales in assessing value chain dynamics and their relationship with agricultural systems.

PRIMA
IN THE MEDITERRANEAN AREA

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HOW WILL LENSES WORK?

Ecosystem Approach

Strengthening renewable energy resilience and food security in the face of climate change by creating a hybrid of agriculture and photovoltaic infrastructure. **The Agrivoltaics** concept will be key to the Nexus approach by simultaneously controlling the physical and biological dimensions.

Benefits to Ecosystem Services

- ✓ Maximise the Water Use Efficiency (WUE).
- ✓ Avoiding photosynthesis depression due to heat and light stress, and in turn.
- ✓ The Agrivoltaic system increases CO2 uptake and fruit production.

"EXPERIMENTAL WATER-ENERGY-FOOD-CLIMATE PILOT" monitoring and participating in the orchard-voltaic experiment documenting and evaluating the technological solutions, the agronomic feasibility to achieve desirable yields and quality, the financial results and future economic sustainability, and some of the regulatory aspects.

FUTURE PERSPECTIVE "CALL TO ACTION"

"The Galilee pilot ambitions to make diversity a more integral part of farming, as reflected in several European policies and global commitments. Translating this ambition into practice will require the necessary know-how and a range of options for optimizing the joint delivery of economic, environmental, and social services by farming. We suggest that this energy- and food-generating ecosystem may become an essential mechanism for maximizing fruit yields, efficiently delivering water to plants and developing renewable energy in dryland environments."

MIGAL Team

PILOT TEAM

MIGAL is involved in many innovative approaches in agriculture, irrigation and energy-saving and in applying research results on experimental farms distributed from -200 meters below sea level to +1200 meters above sea level. Precision Agriculture is implemented with drones, equipment, AI researchers, and algorithms supporting farmers using satellite images and irrigation controls. This allows the analysis and demonstration of all types of fruits and crops.

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13.6. Koiliaris Factsheet

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Project pilot Areas: Koiliaris CZO, Chania (Greece)

OPTIMIZING THE *Water-Ecosystem-Food-Climate* (WEFC) NEXUS IN AVOCADO PLANTATIONS

The Koiliaris river basin is currently affected by various pressures, ranging from soil degradation, torrential events that exceed infiltration rates leading to runoff and flooding, and loss of forests and natural vegetation. Within the overarching objective to build resilient systems, LENSES aims to find solutions that contribute to sustainable growth, thus contributing to food security. For this purpose, LENSES is applying innovative methodologies and strategies, such as nature-based solutions (NbS), to improve ecosystem management. The Water-Ecosystem-Food-Climate nexus (WEFC) is being evaluated, with a special focus on avocado cultivation.

GENERAL CHARACTERIZATION

Koiliaris River Basin →

- ✓ **Location:** Island of Crete.
- ✓ **Koiliaris River:** 36 km, Origin in the White Mountains (altitude exceeds 2,000 m).
- ✓ **Climate:** Mediterranean with hot/dry summer and cold/humid winter.
- ✓ **Precipitation:** 705 mm Average year (447-1032 mm).
- ✓ **Water resources:** Excellent water quality supplied by the White Mountains. In the regions where the Karst system communicates with the sea, the water quality shows higher chloride concentrations.
- ✓ **Land use:** Grasslands 58%, cultivated areas cover 29.4 %, urban 2.8 %, forests 8.5 % and aquatic areas 0.6 %.
- ✓ Most of the population is **engaged in agriculture**. The Main crops cultivated are *olives, oranges, and grapes*.

LENSES GOALS

The main goals are to improve understanding of the Nexus, improve water management and increase adaptive capacity to climate change. The objectives by domain are highlighted below:

Key domain goals →

- ✓ **Water:** Increase irrigation water efficiency by irrigating the tree, not the field, and local stakeholder engagement with government authorities for water management.
- ✓ **Ecosystems:** Increase NbS application, restore/increase biodiversity and reduce environmental pressures on ecosystems.
- ✓ **Food:** Increase food production and drought resilience and improve agricultural infrastructure.

HOW WILL LENSES WORK?

Modelling will be used to run Nature-based Solutions (NbS) scenarios and quantify the impact on the Nexus using hydrological and geochemical data from the Koiliaris-Critical Zone Observatory. LENSES will combine state-of-the-art technology, such as Participatory Systems Dynamic Modeling (PSDM), water accounting, climate risk assessment and NbS bundles, and stakeholder expertise and knowledge.

Priority set of actions →

- ✓ Optimize irrigation systems and increase productivity
- ✓ Learning Alliances and Action (LAA): Focus group (avocado producers) + Participatory workshops
- ✓ Installation of soil moisture probes
- ✓ Running models to simulate plant growth and ecosystem processes
- ✓ Development of innovative business models

FUTURE PERSPECTIVE "CALL TO ACTION"

"It is necessary to have a scientific basis and data to present to institutions that can generate positive change in the agricultural systems of the Basin to address the challenges. We support studies that provide better water and land management, evaluations of soil degradation and soil formation and analyse institutional frameworks and possible barriers. Through monitoring and research, it is expected to assess the Nexus in the Koiliaris Watershed and the Extended Karst. Systematically, it is expected to minimize the environmental footprint and impact of the operation while maximizing the benefits to the farmer and the environment. Finally, Nature-based Solutions (NBS) are crucial in moving toward sustainable development while preserving ecosystems."

Technical University of Crete (TUC)

REGIONAL TEAM

The Technical University of Crete (TUC) is one of Greece's Higher Education Institutions, whose mission is to develop modern engineering specialties, to place emphasis on research in fields of advanced technology as well as to establish close cooperation with industry. The research is conducted at the Hydrogeochemical Engineering and Remediation of Soils (HersLab) laboratory (www.herslab.tuc.gr). The main contribution of TUC is in providing the tools for the modelling of the Nexus and the impacts of climate change and the use of the case study - Koiliaris CZO (<http://www.koiliaris-czo.tuc.gr/>).

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13.7. Deir Alla Factsheet

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Project pilot Areas: Middle Jordan Valley (Jordan)

INTERCROPPED, CROP ROTATION FOR SILAGE MAKING USING MIXED WATER QUALITY: DEVELOPMENT OF FEED QUALITY SOFTWARE.

The Jordan Valley is an intensive irrigated agriculture, where the Dair Alla Agricultural Station is located. Farmers in the area raise livestock to maximize their benefits. The National Agricultural Research Centre (NARC) encourages local farmers to benefit from agricultural by-products to feed their animals and replace part of their land planted with vegetable fodder. At NARC, we plan to develop a feed formulation program with a matrix for a more economical feed ratio for livestock. Agricultural and industrial by-products will be part of the matrix as non-conventional feed resources that can minimize high feed costs through a low-cost feed ration strategy. Farmers will benefit from better use of water to produce intercropped silage and reduce the cost of production in the livestock system.

GENERAL CHARACTERIZATION

Jordan Valley □

- ✓ **Population:** About 605,000.
- ✓ **Climate:** Average annual rainfall is 277 mm. Warm in winter and hot in summer.
- ✓ **Irrigation:** Intensive in vegetables and fruit trees. **Surface water:** Mixture of rainwater and treated wastewater; some farmers use solar energy for irrigation. **Groundwater:** Desalination improves water quality.

Dair-Alla Agricultural Research Station →

- ✓ **Location:** Center of the Jordan Valley.
- ✓ **Primary source of Irrigation water:** King Talal Dam. Salinity ranges from 1.8 dSm^{-1} in winter to about 3.0 dSm^{-1} in summer, resulting in salinity accumulation in the root zone profile and deterioration of productivity if not properly managed.

HOW WILL LENSES WORK?

- ✓ Support the allocation of resources for **Sustainable Development**.
- ✓ LENSES will develop **innovative methodologies** that contribute to the needs, and one of them is to improve the production of feed for livestock.
- ✓ **Improve resource management:** The aim is to increase farmers' benefits and improve the state of ecosystems by reducing pollution. For example, improved water allocation efficiency reduces leakage, and alternative energy sources reduce the cost of production.
- ✓ Apply **Nature-based Solutions (NBS)** to mitigate Climate Change, salinity accumulation and soil deterioration.

KEY Sustainable Development Goals

FUTURE PERSPECTIVE "CALL TO ACTION"

"We believe that it is essential to apply new methodologies to achieve the Sustainable Development Goals by integrating environmental aspects to improve the situation of farmers in the Jordan Valley. In this case, a close collaboration between the farmers' union and the water user associations is essential. A detailed assessment of optimal silage production of the best quality will be developed, accompanied by a thorough social and economic analysis to help farmers decide on crop rotation techniques. Crop rotation will have a positive impact, such as improved yields. The production of new forages and mixtures for livestock feed will demonstrate and be a reference example of the importance of good management."

NARC Team

COUNTRY PILOTS REGIONAL TEAM

NARC is a distinguished governmental scientific institution with different disciplines for agricultural research to optimize the use of available resources and achieve sustainable agricultural growth. NARC aims to improve agricultural production, conserve natural resources, and maintain food sufficiency and ecological balance. NARC has discrete geographic stations distributed over the country with good infrastructure, equipment and laboratories networks equipped with modern devices. NARC has strong local, regional and international relations and has its regulations.

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13.8. Lessons Learned videos

The [LENSES Stories YouTube channel](#) has expanded its offerings with a captivating series of short videos intended to shed light on the efforts of our pilot teams. These engaging videos serve as a bridge between our projects and the general public and are easily accessible through YouTube.

[Doñana Lessons Learned](#)

[Tarquinia Lessons Learned](#)

[Menemen Lessons Learned](#)

[Pinios Lessons Learned](#)

[Koiliaris Lessons Learned](#)

[Deir Alla Lessons Learned](#)

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